

Policy for retrofit needs to support place-based and inclusive supply chain, employment and skills strategies

This supplementary information summarizes the key themes and takeaways from a series of discussions held as part of an SSH-STEM collaborative workshop on retrofitting homes. Information on the expertise and interests of participants who contributed throughout the workshop can be found in the supplementary document [SI_workshop_participants_expertise_interests.xlsx](#).

Building a skilled workforce for retrofitting requires a multi-pronged approach that addresses both technical and social challenges. Collaborative efforts across government, industry, training providers, and community organizations are needed to develop a diverse, skilled workforce capable of delivering high-quality retrofitting projects across the EU. This will ensure a sustainable future for the housing sector and contribute towards the green agenda.

Challenges

- **Skills Gap:** The current construction sector lacks the expertise to deliver large-scale retrofitting projects. Training programs need to equip workers with the necessary technical skills, but also foster collaborative work practices and a cultural shift towards sustainability.
- **Diversity and Inclusion:** The workforce is not diverse, with low representation of women, minorities, and young people. Strategies are needed to attract a wider range of talent, including outreach programs, targeted training, and addressing unconscious bias within the industry.
- **Quality and Standards:** Inconsistent quality standards and a lack of licensing create uncertainty for both homeowners and contractors. Establishing minimum licensing requirements and clear quality standards will be crucial.
- **Policy and Coordination:** National policy needs better translation and implementation at the local level. There's a lack of coordination between different sectors and organizations, requiring a more collaborative approach.
- **Supply Chain:** Difficulty reaching installers and integrating them into the retrofitting ecosystem. Rising costs and short-term project focus threaten the sustainability of the supply chain.

Potential solutions and recommendations

- **Skills Development:** Invest in training programs that combine technical skills with collaborative work practices and cultural change. Training should be designed to meet the needs of both new entrants and the existing workforce.
- **Targeted Training:** Develop training solutions tailored to the specific needs of different roles within the retrofitting sector. This could include apprenticeships, short courses, and mentoring programs.
- **Standards and Licensing:** Implement minimum licensing requirements for key trades involved in retrofitting. Establish clear quality standards for retrofit work to ensure consistency and consumer protection.
- **Public Sector Leadership:** Leverage public procurement to drive demand for high-quality work and promote best practices. Local authorities and social housing organizations can play a leading role in setting standards and supporting skills development.

- **Collaboration and Outreach:** Foster collaboration between public and private sectors, training providers, and community organizations. Develop strategies to attract a diverse workforce and ensure outreach to under-represented groups, including women, minorities, and young people.
- **Streamlined Processes:** Simplify public procurement processes and documentation to facilitate participation by SMEs. This will allow smaller contractors to contribute to retrofitting projects.
- **Sustainable Funding:** Allocate long-term funding for training, quality control, and repair and maintenance work. Secure funding that goes beyond short-term cycles to ensure a stable and skilled workforce.
- **Knowledge Sharing:** Facilitate knowledge sharing across the sector, including best practices, successful models, and lessons learned. This could involve workshops, online resources, and networking events.

Further considerations

- **Communication Strategies:** The importance of clear communication strategies, including short videos and toolkits, to effectively train workers at different levels.
- **National Policy Framework:** The need for a well-coordinated national policy framework with effective implementation plans at the local level. Clear national strategies will guide local efforts and ensure consistency across each state.
- **Mapping Resources:** The importance of mapping existing resources and organizations involved in retrofitting skills development to avoid duplication and ensure comprehensive coverage. By identifying existing resources, a more coordinated approach can be developed.

Session 1: National Policy to Local Skills for Retrofitting Buildings

This session focused on the challenges and opportunities of developing a skilled workforce to deliver large-scale building retrofits. A multi-pronged approach is needed to address the skills gap in the retrofit sector. This includes national policy changes, increased investment in training, improved standards, and better coordination across different sectors and levels of government. Only through such a collaborative effort can each state build a skilled workforce capable of delivering the large-scale retrofitting needed for a sustainable future.

National Policy and Skills Gap:

- The government aims for at least 55% of retrofit interventions to target the worst performing buildings.
- However, a significant skills gap exists, with current training systems failing to equip workers with the necessary expertise.
- Initiatives like BUILD UP Skills aim to bridge this gap through skills pacts, EU support, and a focus on green and digital transitions in the construction sector.

Workforce Challenges:

- The retrofit sector lacks diversity, with low representation of women, LGBT+ individuals, and young people.
- An aging workforce is nearing retirement, and replacements are scarce.
- Low job security and wages make the sector unattractive to many.

Solutions and Recommendations:

- Develop a pipeline for retrofit work, including social housing programs, government funding schemes, and public sector projects.
- Establish regional centers of excellence for training, avoiding duplication of efforts.
- Integrate retrofit skills training into all relevant roles within the construction sector.
- Partner with architects, surveyors, and training providers like DWP.
- Encourage young people by promoting well-paid, impactful careers in the green sector.
- Develop new apprenticeship programs with clear career paths, including financial incentives like "earn while you learn" schemes.
- Reform existing apprenticeship programs to address low wages and poor working conditions.
- Establish minimum standards and licensing for key trades involved in retrofitting.

Policy and Procurement:

- Leverage public procurement to drive voluntary standards and encourage training in the sector.
- Local authorities need support in developing expertise and managing large-scale retrofit projects.
- Standardize procurement processes to ensure skills development is reflected on the ground.
- Utilize frameworks like PAS 2035 to define good practice in retrofitting.

Regulation and Standards:

- Implement clear and consistent regulations for the retrofit workforce, connecting skills and competencies to national standards.
- Consider a licensing system for tradespeople in the sector to ensure quality.
- Develop and implement product certifications to guarantee compatibility and effectiveness of retrofitting materials.

Government Action:

- Provide strong, clear signals and long-term funding for skills development and training programs.
- Focus on fuel poverty initiatives to incentivize retrofitting.
- Streamline funding streams to avoid inefficient project prioritization due to short-term funding cycles.

STEM Coordination and Collaboration:

- Ensure national policy can be effectively translated and implemented at the local level.
- Encourage collaboration between FE colleges, local authorities, and industry stakeholders.
- Develop a clear and concise set of policy asks in education and harmonization for governments to facilitate effective action.

Session 2: Building a Diverse and Inclusive Workforce for Retrofitting

This session explored strategies for increasing diversity and inclusion within the retrofitting workforce. Building a diverse and inclusive workforce for retrofitting requires a multi-faceted approach. By addressing existing challenges, implementing targeted strategies, and promoting a broader message of impact, the sector can attract a wider range of talent and ensure a skilled workforce for the future.

Challenges:

- Other European member states rely less on apprenticeships compared to the UK, creating a different model for skills development.
- A significant gap exists between professional and operative roles in the construction sector, limiting career progression.
- Traditional apprenticeship programs are declining, with few college leavers finding employment in construction.

Success Stories:

- Glasgow City Building showcases a unique model of direct labor by a local authority, involving unions and employing a diverse workforce, including people with disabilities.
- Her Own Space highlights the need to engage women homeowners and tradeswomen in retrofit projects.
- Real-world examples demonstrate the passion of women in the retrofit sector but emphasize the need to reassure them of opportunities.

Strategies for Inclusion:

- Mentorship programs: Pair experienced workers with newcomers for on-site training and support.
- Diversity and Inclusion Training: Equip existing workforce with skills to interact effectively with diverse teams.
- Outreach Programs: Target under-represented groups like refugees through targeted training and cultural sensitivity support (translators, trainers).
- Mobile Training Units: Bring training directly to communities to overcome accessibility barriers.
- Community Building: Foster social connections and shared interests to build trust and encourage participation.

Messaging and Incentives:

- Focus on the broader impact of retrofitting beyond just green jobs - highlight benefits for homes, occupant health, and overall well-being.
- Promote cultural competence within the sector, ensuring retrofit professionals understand and can effectively serve diverse communities.
- Encourage employers to actively support the inclusion of under-represented groups and challenge internal resistance.

Potential Long-Term Vision:

- Inspire young people, particularly girls, about careers in construction and retrofitting.
- Develop role models and positive messaging that resonate with diverse audiences.

Session 3: Building a Sustainable Supply Chain for Retrofitting

This session focused on building a robust and sustainable supply chain for retrofitting projects. By implementing quality standards, streamlining processes, and promoting knowledge sharing, the sector can create a robust network of qualified professionals to deliver successful retrofit projects.

Challenges:

- Engaging installers: Difficulty reaching installers outside of trade associations, leading to a limited pool of qualified professionals.
- Frustration among low-carbon architects: Needing to educate contractors who lack basic retrofitting knowledge. This disrupts workflows and creates inefficiencies.
- Cost of living impacting supply chain: Rising material costs and economic pressures affecting the availability and affordability of skilled labor.
- Short-term focus on skills: Emphasis on immediate skill acquisition overshadows the need for high-quality jobs with good working conditions.

Solutions and Recommendations:

- Customer focus: Prioritize homeowner needs through surveys and feedback mechanisms.
- Targeted outreach: Develop strategies to reach unaffiliated installers through engagement events and business support initiatives.
- Standardized quality: Establish a basic quality standard for retrofitting work to create market demand for good practices.
- Public sector leadership: Leverage the public sector, like social housing and local authorities, to drive demand for high-quality work through procurement policies.
- Independent quality control: Develop an independent body, potentially involving universities, to oversee and ensure quality standards.
- Sustainable funding: Allocate budget for ongoing repair and maintenance work to maintain a healthy supply chain.
- Cooperative models: Explore models like Retrofit Works, where workers are incentivized to identify and bring in new retrofit leads.

Collaboration and Streamlining:

- Facilitate knowledge sharing between public and private sectors to optimize training and skill development.
- Support SME contractors in transitioning from small-scale projects to larger retrofit works (e.g., Green Homes Grant skills provision).
- Streamline public procurement processes to be more accessible for SMEs by reducing excessive documentation requirements.
- Encourage collaboration between Tier 1 contractors and smaller suppliers through local authority initiatives like Durham County Council's program.
- Invest in training for procurement staff within local authorities to ensure they can effectively source and manage retrofit projects.
- Establish umbrella organizations to assist smaller contractors with administrative tasks, PAS compliance, and overall project management.